

Abstract

A possible earthquake predictor found in an experiment involving graphite particles in carbonated water.

Experiments on seismic activity

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1 Intro

Can earthquakes be predicted? According to Complete Relativity[1] (CR), everything is relatively predictable. The question is, can an observer, as limited as humans, predict earthquakes and how far ahead? I argue that this is possible. One way is subconscious precognition, which, as evidence suggests, certainly exists, however, this is obviously limited to specific subspecies and individuals of species, and in humans may not be reliable. But other ways may be possible, and a potential way was discovered while I was making experiments unrelated to seismic activity.

2 Experimentum: Sensus fidelium

An earthquake of 4.0 Richter magnitude occurred at my location (epicenter distance < 15 km) 3 days after measurements started. A week later, another earthquake of magnitude 3.0 occurred.

After subsequent analysis of measurements, a possible correlation with increased seismic activity was discovered. Setup:

1. Carbonated mineral water poured into a glass jar,
2. Residue from pencil sharpening (mostly fine graphite particles) added to the solution (on top, no stirring),
3. Jar lid closed.

2.1 Methodology, observation and measurements

The observation covers a period of 2 weeks in the month of June 2018., multiple jars with carbonated water containing various ion concentrations at room temperature. Observed phenomena:

- oscillatory (sinusoidal) vertical motion of graphite particles with various but consistent frequencies ($\approx 0.01 - 0.1$ Hz) and amplitudes,

- observed duration of oscillation \approx 10 - 70 minutes,
- magnitude of activity different between jars,
- deflection from 90° angle detected in some oscillations,
- activity ranges from somewhat rich to sparse (usually a single particle oscillating at any time, with up to a couple of hours between events),
- event probability decreasing with CO₂ evaporation (buildup of pressure above the water).

At the start of the experiment, carbonated water was poured into a glass jar, graphite particles were added on top and the lid was closed. Due to significant initial CO₂ bubbling, measurements were only taken after there was no visible CO₂ evaporation.

The solution was sporadically inspected for activity, which, once detected, was continuously monitored with a pair of healthy eyes, and measured using common ruler and a digital stopwatch.

Measured and deduced quantities include: period, velocity, amplitude, frequency.

Measurements started on 2018.06.04 and the experiment ended on 2018.06.18. During measurements weather was calm (no lightning strikes). Details of first

solution	event	event start	event end	duration [h:m]	T [s]	s _z [cm]	f [Hz]	λ _e [m]
M0	M0-1	2018.06.04 13:15	2018.06.04 13:36	0:21	40	1	0.025	13720
M	M-1	2018.06.14 15:15	2018.06.14 16:15	1:00	11.2	5.1	0.089285714	3841.6
D	D-1	2018.06.15 15:20	2018.06.15 16:20	1:00	60	4.9	0.016666667	20580
M	M-2	2018.06.16 16:30	2018.06.16 17:00	0:30	36	5.2	0.027777778	12348

Table 1: Measurements of sinusoidal activity

four measurements are shown in Table 1. Also shown is the calculated wavelength of a sound wave in air corresponding to measured frequency f:

$$\lambda_e = \frac{c_s}{f}$$

$$c_s = \text{speed of sound in air at } 20^\circ\text{C} = 343 \text{ m/s}$$

Uncertainty in period (T) measurement: ± 0.5 s.

Measurements of amplitude hint at possible discreteness in value - measured vertical component (s_z) was concentrated around 1, 5, 8 and 8.5 cm, while horizontal components were generally not significant and were not measured.

Two earthquakes occurred during the experiment, as shown in Table 2.

2.2 Analysis and hypothesis

Graphite is hydrophobic and a good electrical conductor. The mechanics might be explained through binding (adsorption) of ions (Na⁺, K⁺, ..) on graphite surface and interaction of the system with CO₂ evaporation.

event	date	magnitude (Richter)	depth [km]	coordinates [°]	distance [m]	sources
SB1	2018.06.07 08:45	4.0	4	45.3 N, 18 E	13890	a[2], b[3], c[4]
SB3	2018.06.14 00:49	3.0	-	45.27 N 17.9 E	8770	d[5], e[6]

Table 2: Data on earthquakes occurred during the experiment (also showing distance of epicenter to experiment location)

A vertical difference in electric potential is generated in the solution due to affinity for positive ion enrichment on graphite surface - cation- π interaction.

This might cause or accelerate the downward movement of bound particles.

At some point the CO₂ bubble propels the system upwards, without breaking the bond (note that the bubble at the time of measurements was usually not visible, but it is hypothesized to be there based on observation when CO₂ bubbling was visible).

Near the surface, the bubble is detached or fragmented, released CO₂ evaporates and the process repeats.

Thus, the activity stops with the exhaustion of CO₂, or when evaporation pressure becomes lower than electric field pressure.

Although the events seem to be correlated with CO₂ evaporation, conservation of frequency, amplitude (regular sinusoidal oscillation), duration of stable oscillation and observed angular deflection in some events might indicate detection of low frequency EM waves and a possible response to fluctuations in Earth's magnetic field.

In most of such stable long lived oscillations particles did not reach the surface at any point, but some that did reach the surface did not immediately go down although the oscillation frequency remained consistent - this cutoff in amplitude strongly suggests EM wave absorption (otherwise the particle would go down as soon as CO₂ is released, not pulled down couple of moments later).

If kinetic energy is the result of EM wave absorption, the frequency of the wave must be equal to the cyclotron resonance frequency of the *carbon* system (carbon is present in both graphite and CO₂).

Note that low frequency EM waves in the range 0.01 - 0.5 Hz were previously observed before strong earthquakes[7].

Cyclotron resonance frequency (f_c) of a carbon atom (ion) in a magnetic field 1000 times weaker than Earth's magnetic field at the location of the experiment is equal to the average value of measured frequencies:

$$f_c = \frac{zqB}{2\pi m} = \frac{1}{1000} \frac{zqB_e}{2\pi m_c} = 0.05 Hz$$

$$z = \text{number of charges of the ion} = 1$$

$$q = 1.60217733 * 10^{-19} C$$

$$B_e = 42 \mu T$$

$$m_c = \text{carbon atom mass} = 1.992646547 * 10^{-26} kg$$

where B_e is the dominant (vertical) component (D-U) of Earth's magnetic field strength at the location (45.189917 °N, 17.916138 °E, 127m elevation) at the time of experiment[8].

For the horizontal N-S component of the magnetic field ($B_e = 23 \mu\text{T}$), the frequency is 0.03 Hz (which is even equal to one of the measured frequencies in the experiment).

Note that a field resulting in the measured average frequency (for $z/m = 1/m_c$) is 42 nT - magnetic pulses of such magnitude have been previously observed before earthquakes, and associated with geophysical semiconductor processes[9].

However, it is unlikely that the system is resonating with such pulses due to much longer duration.

I do not know what is the actual z/m ratio in the oscillating system of these particles but I did observe the bubble changing in size during oscillation (at times when the bubble was visible).

It is thus not only possible that the system is resonating during a long lived disturbance in Earth's magnetic field, but even a stable Earth's magnetic field - in the following way:

- the CO_2 accumulates on the graphite ion compound until z/m ratio becomes $1/1000$,
- at that point the system is absorbing EM waves and begins oscillating,
- the CO_2 remains attached (in required amount) during EM wave emission, but eventually, as CO_2 in the solution evaporates, the required amount cannot be sustained and the system loses ability to oscillate.

The signal M0-1 is the only one measured before the SB1 earthquake. Interestingly, wavelength of a wave traveling at the speed of sound (in air) λ_e at measured frequency of M0-1 is almost equal to SB1 epicenter distance.

Also interesting is that speed of diffusion of electrical disturbances (positively charged *holes*) through rocks (100 - 200 m/s) due to broken peroxy bonds (postulated as a source of mentioned magnetic pulses detected before earthquakes) equal to 100 m/s gives a wavelength exactly equal to hypocenter depth (4 km).

The signal may thus be interpreted as an electric wave traveling vertically from the hypocenter to surface and emission of a sound wave of the same frequency upon reaching the surface.

This would require:

- some kind of entanglement (dipole) of hypocenter-surface momenta,
- conversion of sound pressure into EM pressure at detector.

Due to above requirements, I find this interpretation unlikely.

But I do not believe in coincidence either:

- I have started the experiment couple of days before the earthquake, and I've never performed such experiments before,
- earthquakes are very rare here (although, this should change as I expect global increase in frequency of earthquakes due to neurogenesis),
- the only signal measured before the earthquake has a sound wavelength equal to epicenter distance and electric wavelength equal to hypocenter depth,
- both type of waves are frequently associated with earthquakes.

Thus, I interpret this as a typical event of synchronicity, a sign(al) that M0-1 has the earthquake precursor characteristics and that it was indeed the precursor to SB1.

If correlation of sinusoidal activity with seismic activity is confirmed with further testing, this could turn into an inexpensive solution for earthquake prediction.

3 Follow up experiments

3.1 Exp. 2020/01

The experiment was repeated with a single jar of carbonated mineral water, almost two years later (2020.05.06 - 2020.05.15), at the same location.

The peculiar motion was detected again, but it was slower and no regular long lived sinusoidal oscillation was observed.

I am unsure of the sensitivity of the instrument. The 5.5 magnitude earthquake occurred 200 km away (in Zagreb) on 2020.03.22 which was also felt at the experiment location.

The ground in Zagreb was still seismically active when the experiment was actually performed (2 months later) - around the time of the experiment the earthquakes of magnitude 2 - 3 were occurring in Zagreb.

This goes in favor of hypothesis of correlation of seismic activity with the oscillation, which was now, as the activity, weaker.

Interestingly, at times the particles would align and remain suspended along a particular plane:

Such alignment is shown on Fig. 1, where particles are aligned in a plane 15° from horizontal. The alignment was not sudden and was long lived, although

Figure 1: Plane alignment of graphite particles

possible rotation of the plane was observed couple of hours later (not all particles remained on the plane).

As can be seen on Fig. 1, the particles were either along the plane or at the surface, confirming polarization of submerged particles - as hypothesized before.

3.2 Exp. 2020/02

Experiment performed 2020.07.30 - 2020.08.05. No activity.

3.3 Other

I have performed 2 more experiments, one in August, other in September. There was no activity. The last experiment was not finished though as the glass jar got broken.

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